

Mean prediction at 2100: *Adelotus brevis*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Assa darlingtoni*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Austrochaperina adelphe*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Austrochaperina fryi*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Austrochaperina gracilipes*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Austrochaperina pluvialis*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Cophixalus australis*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Cophixalus bombiens*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Cophixalus infacetus*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Cophixalus ornatus*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Crinia bilingua*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Crinia deserticola*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Crinia flindersensis*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Crinia georgiana*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Crinia glauerti*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Crinia insignifera*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Crinia remota*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Crinia riparia*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Crinia signifera*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Crinia sloanei*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Crinia subinsignifera*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Crinia tasmaniensis*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Crinia tinnula*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Cyclorana alboguttata*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Cyclorana australis*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Cyclorana brevipes*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Cyclorana cryptotis*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Cyclorana cultripes*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Cyclorana longipes*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Cyclorana maini*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Cyclorana manya*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Cyclorana platycephala*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Cyclorana verrucosa*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Geocrinia leai*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Geocrinia victoriana*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Heleioporus australiacus*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Heleioporus eyrei*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Lechriodus fletcheri*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Limnodynastes convexiusculus*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Limnodynastes depressus*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Limnodynastes dorsalis*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Limnodynastes dumerilii*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Limnodynastes fletcheri*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Limnodynastes interioris*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Limnodynastes lignarius*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Limnodynastes peronii*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Limnodynastes salmini*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Limnodynastes terraereginae*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria adelaidensis*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria aurea*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria barringtonensis*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria bella*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria bicolor*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria booroolongensis*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria brevipalmata*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria burrowsae*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria caerulea*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria castanea*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria chloris*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria citropa*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria cooloolensis*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria coplandi*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria cyclorhyncha*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria dahlii*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria daviesae*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria dayi*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria dentata*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria electrica*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria eucnemis*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria ewingii*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria fallax*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria freycineti*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria gilleni*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria gracilentata*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria inermis*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria infrafrenata*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria jervisiensis*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria jungguy*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria latopalmata*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria littlejohni*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria meiriana*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria microbelos*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria moorei*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria nannotis*

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria nasuta*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria nigrofrenata*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria nyakalensis*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria olongburensis*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria pallida*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria paraewingi*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria pearsoniana*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria peronii*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria phyllochroa*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria raniformis*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria revelata*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria rheocola*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria rothii*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria serrata*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria subglandulosa*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria tornieri*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria tyleri*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria verreauxii*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria watjulumensis*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria wilcoxii*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Litoria xanthomera*

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Metacrinia nichollsi*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Mixophyes coggeri*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Mixophyes fasciolatus*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Mixophyes iteratus*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Mixophyes schevilli*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Myobatrachus gouldii*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Neobatrachus pictus*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Neobatrachus sutor*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Notaden bennettii*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Notaden melanoscaphus*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Notaden nichollsi*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Papurana daemeli*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Paracrinia haswelli*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Platyplectrum ornatum*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Platyplectrum spenceri*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Pseudophryne australis*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Pseudophryne bibronii*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Pseudophryne coriacea*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Pseudophryne dendyi*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Pseudophryne major*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Pseudophryne raveni*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Pseudophryne robinsoni*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Pseudophryne semimarmorata*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Taudactylus acutirostris*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Uperoleia altissima*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Uperoleia arenicola*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Uperoleia fusca*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Uperoleia inundata*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Uperoleia laevis*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Uperoleia littlejohni*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Uperoleia mahonyi*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Uperoleia martini*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Uperoleia mimula*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Uperoleia rugosa*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Uperoleia trachyderma*

SSP126

SSP370

Elevation (m)

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.

Mean prediction at 2100: *Uperoleia tyleri*

SSP126

SSP370

Purple = currently occupied, projected to be lost.
Red = currently occupied and predicted to be maintained.
Orange = predicted novel environment.